
IMPROVING TEACHERS' MATHEMATICS INSTRUCTION THROUGH THE APPLICATION OF METACOGNITIVE SKILLS

By

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Abstract

The study examined how secondary school mathematics teachers apply metacognitive skills and strategies in their instructional practices and how this influences the improvement of their pedagogical knowledge. A sample of 45 teachers was randomly selected using the hat draw method. Data was collected via a structured questionnaire focused on teachers' application of metacognitive skills and strategies, measured on a four-point Likert scale. Experts validated the instrument, and its reliability coefficient ($r = 0.81$) was established using the Spearman-Brown formula. Data analysis employed descriptive statistics (mean) and Pearson's Product Moment Correlation to test the null hypothesis, yielding a significant correlation coefficient ($r = 0.672$). The findings support the recommendation that metacognitive strategies should be systematically integrated into teacher education programs across Nigerian universities, colleges of education, polytechnics, and institutions overseeing basic education to foster continuous professional development.

Keywords: Metacognitive Skills, Mathematics Instruction, Teacher Development, Instructional Improvement, Teaching Strategies

Introduction

Metacognition is broadly defined as one's awareness and control over their own cognitive processes (Flavell, 1979, cited in Kaplan et al., 2013), often simplified as "thinking about one's thinking." Well-developed metacognitive abilities are linked to enhanced learning outcomes, especially in mathematics education. Globally, and notably in Nigeria, mathematics instruction suffers from traditional, teacher-centered methods that hinder conceptual understanding (Ojose, 2011; Stacey & Turner, 2015; Suciati & Febriyanti, 2020). In the United States, for instance, only half of high school graduates enroll in mathematics courses beyond Grade 10, with ineffective instructional methods cited as a contributing factor (NCTM, 2000). Research indicates that poor teaching strategies, lack of student motivation, and ineffective problem-solving approaches in countries like Jordan and Nigeria undermine mathematics education (Altakhayneh, 2020). The role of metacognition in mathematics is increasingly recognized as crucial for developing cognitive abilities such as reasoning, decision-making, and problem-solving (Akaydin et al., 2020). This study, set in Gusau Local Government Area of Zamfara State, investigates how teachers' pedagogical knowledge can be enhanced through metacognitive strategies to improve learners' outcomes in mathematics (Tambara, 2015; Tachie, 2019).

Effective teaching requires an integration of both subject content knowledge (SCK) and pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) (Shulman, 1986; Ngcoza, 2013). Teachers with robust pedagogical and content knowledge can become more adaptable, confident, and effective in facilitating learning (Rigelman, 2007; Mishra & Koehler, 2006). Scholars such as Anthony & Walshaw (2009) emphasize that mathematics' ubiquity across disciplines necessitates strengthening teachers' instructional capabilities through targeted development of relevant metacognitive strategies.

Visser et al. (2015) argue that identifying factors impeding learners' performance is critical for policy makers and teachers striving to improve mathematics outcomes. Other studies (Altakhayneh, 2020; Ojose, 2011; Webb, 2010) underline the necessity of approaches in teaching mathematics that prioritize dedication, patience, and strategic classroom practices (Myerson et al., 2007).

The persistent underperformance in mathematics at both local and international levels continues to concern educational bodies globally (Ercikan et al., 2005; Sweeting, 2011). Effective teaching methods are crucial for improving learners' abilities. Pre-service and in-service teacher training must prioritize both content and pedagogical development (Kilpatrick et al., 2001). Teachers with high self-efficacy tend to exhibit better classroom management, positive attitudes, and effectiveness in fostering learner achievement.

Studies from South Africa highlight that outdated teaching methods emphasizing rote memorization over problem-solving skills remain prevalent despite the Curriculum and Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS) introduced in 2011 (Department of Basic Education (DBE), 2011; Sanni, 2007). CAPS emphasizes student-centered learning that cultivates mathematical competence, creativity, and appreciation. Similarly, the global demand for critical thinking and problem-solving necessitates integrating metacognitive strategies within mathematics instruction (Kember et al., 2006). Mathematical proficiency goes beyond procedural knowledge; teachers must unpack and communicate mathematical concepts clearly, enabling learners to grasp underlying principles (Schuck, 1999; Kilpatrick et al., 2001). Strategies like problem-based learning promote meaningful engagement, helping

students develop skills required for future workplace demands (Boyatzis et al., 2002; Darling-Hammond et al., 2020). Despite curricular reforms, implementation gaps persist as many teachers fail to apply effective strategies that nurture learners' problem-solving abilities (Shulman, 1986; Anthony & Walshaw, 2009). Metacognitive strategies, such as the use of acronyms, open-ended problems, and collaborative discussions, have been found effective in enhancing learners' abilities to articulate and refine their thought processes (Tachie, 2019; Uberti et al., 2004). Such approaches encourage learners to reflect on their cognitive processes and improve problem-solving skills.

Objective of the study

The study aimed at:

1. Finding out how best the metacognitive skills and their application help for effective teaching and learning of mathematics

Research Question

The study aims at finding answer to the following question:

1. How are the metacognitive skills and their application related towards the contribution in effective teaching and learning of mathematics?

Research Hypothesis

In line with the research question, the following null hypothesis that guides the study was tested at 5% level of significance ($P \leq 0.05$):

HO: There is no significant relationship in the application of metacognitive skills and the effective teaching and learning of mathematics.

Methodology

The research design used for the conduct of this study was a survey method. This is because the method can be used to collect data from a relatively large number of cases at a particular time (Best & James (1985) in Wushishi, 2010). As the study involved all Nigerian Teachers in Secondary Schools, both male and female. However, the researchers used the Government Girls Day Secondary School, Tutun wada, Government Day Secondary School Damba, Government Girl Day Secondary School Damba, Government Day Sambo Secondary School, Tudun Wada and Government Girls Day Secondary School, Samaru , Gusau as a sample and conducted a survey of opinion at random. For the purpose of collecting data, the researchers developed a questionnaire based on four-point Likert type scale. The points on the scale are SA= Strongly Agree (4 points); A= Agree (3 points); D= Disagree (2points); SD=Strongly Disagree (1 point). The questionnaire comprises of ten (10) items question/ statement aimed at finding out the extent metacognitive skills and their application help in ensuring effective teaching and learning of mathematics. The questionnaire was administered on the randomly selected sample of respondents by the researchers. During the analysis, statements with a mean of 2.50 (*Creterion reference mean*) or greater were accepted/agreed upon, otherwise rejected/disagreed. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test the null hypothesis

Result

The questionnaire consisted of ten (10) statements. About forty five (45) questionnaire were randomly distributed among sampled schools (Secondary School Teachers), this is because of the limited number of mathematics teachers in the state, However, only thirty five (35) duly completed ones were collected back and the data analysis was carried out on them. The results of data analysis were presented on table 3 which answered the research questions.

Table 1: Analysis of Administered and Returned Instrument per School (Mathematics Teachers) on Teachers' Skills and Strategies application of metacognition

S/N	Name of sampled Schools	Number of Questionnaire administered	Number of Questionnaire returned/collected
1	GDSS Dan Turai	5	5
2	GGDSS Tudun Wada	7	5
3	GGDSS Damba	5	4
4	GDSS Damba	7	5
5	GGDSS Samaru	7	5
6	GDSSSS Tudun Wada	6	5
7	GDSS Ibrahim Gusau	8	6
		Total=45	Total=35

Table 2: Respondent's opinion on Teachers' Skills and Strategies application of metacognition

<i>Statement</i>	<i>SA</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>N</i>
1. Selecting teaching and learning materials/resources relevant to the topic to be taught helps in TLM	20	11	2	1	35
2. Considering learners' prior knowledge first before teaching any new topic/concept help in TLM	20	15	0	0	35
3. Considering learners' cultural background help a lot in TLM	16	17	1	1	35
4. Planning lesson well before going to class and ensuring that relevant information are provided for the learners in class help in TLM	25	10	0	0	35
5. Paying special attention to learners with barriers to learning help in TLM	13	21	1	0	35

6. Solving all the mathematical problems myself and prepare the answers in at least two different ways before presenting to students help a lot in TLM	11	22	1	1	35
7. Monitoring learners' discussions and giving input where necessary during problem solving help a lot in TLM	16	18	1	0	35
8. Encouraging learners to use different strategies in solving mathematics problems help a lot in TLM	15	19	0	1	35
9. Welcoming learners' contribution during lessons plays an important role in TLM	20	14	1	0	35
10. Recap of the lesson if learners did not understand it helps a lot in TLM	17	16	1	1	35

Source: Field work

Table 3: Mean Analysis of Instrument (Teachers' Skills and Strategies application of metacognition)

S/N	Statement	Mean
1	Selecting relevant teaching and learning materials/resources relevant to the topic to be taught help in TLM	3.37
2	Considering learners' prior knowledge first before teaching any new topic/concept help in TLM	3.47
3	Considering learners' cultural background help a lot in TLM	3.37
4	Planning lesson well before going to class and ensuring that relevant information are provided for the learners in class help in TLM	3.71
5	Paying special attention to learners with barriers to learning help in TLM	3.34
6	Solving all the mathematical problems myself and prepare the answers in at least two different ways before presenting to students help a lot in TLM	3.23
7	Monitoring learners' discussions and giving input where necessary during problem solving help a lot in TLM	3.43
8	Encouraging learners to use different strategies in solving mathematics problems help a lot in TLM	3.37
9	Welcoming learners' contribution during lessons help a lot in TLM	3.54
10	Recap of the lesson if learners did not understand it help a lot in TLM	3.40

Source: Field work

Table 4: Result of Hypothesis Testing

Variable	N	Correl. Coefficient (r)	Alpha value	P.value	Decision
Metacognitive Skills	35	0.672	0.05	0.000	H ₀ Rejected
Teaching & Learning Effectiveness					

Discussion of Findings

The result in table 3 shows that all the statements answered our research question as the mean of each statement is greater than the reference mean of 2.50, that is metacognitive skills and their application help for effective teaching and learning of mathematics, and at the same time enhances teachers' pedagogical knowledge of teaching mathematics. Also, table 4, with r which is the correlation coefficient of value 0.672 shows a moderate to strong positive relationship between metacognitive skills and effective teaching and learning of mathematics and $p = 0.000 < 0.05$ indicates that this result is statistically significant and as such the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected. The more teachers apply metacognitive strategies, the more effective teaching and learning outcomes are achieved.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The results from the research suggest that most teachers in this study incorporated many meta-cognitive skills and strategies (such as planning, monitoring, and reflection) which improved their pedagogical knowledge, and this further assisted the mathematical problem-solving skills of their learners. This was done through the help of teachers' questioning methods, monitoring of learners' discussions, supporting learners' trial-and-error methods, and spontaneously thinking about their own thinking among others. The overall result shows that teachers who integrate metacognitive strategies such as planning, monitoring, encouraging multiple approaches, and reflecting with learners achieve better teaching outcomes in mathematics. These strategies foster active learner engagement, help address diverse learning needs, and promote clarity in mathematics instruction. The strong correlation confirms the importance of metacognitive approaches in enhancing teaching effectiveness and student learning. Teachers believe metacognitive strategies strongly enhance effective teaching and learning of mathematics. Statistical evidence confirms a significant and positive relationship between the use of metacognitive skills and improved mathematics instruction. Metacognitive skill would be the potential impact in like Enhancing mathematical literacy, that is students will develop a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts, Increased competitiveness, in doing that Nigerian students will be better equipped to compete globally, Socio-economic benefits and this means that Improved mathematics education can contribute to Nigeria's economic growth and development.

From the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made: It is recommended that the use of metacognitive skills and strategies for developing teachers' pedagogical knowledge of teaching mathematics can be adapted to the Nigerian context, also Universities, Colleges of Education Polytechnics and those in charge of Basic Education could collaborate to maintain the quality of development of teachers' pedagogical knowledge of teaching mathematics through regular metacognitive skills and strategies application. This could be done effectively by engaging teachers in professional development exercises whereby teachers can observe their colleagues teaching and therefore help them to share their problems in a way that has the potential that could lead to changes in teachers' values and conceptions of teaching and learning of mathematics which impact their pedagogical practices meaningfully in the teaching and learning of mathematics in schools. In addition to the above, the government should integrate metacognitive skill in the following ways: Provide educators with professional development opportunities to learn and incorporate metacognitive strategies in mathematics instruction, Revise the mathematics curriculum to emphasize metacognitive skills, problem-solving, and critical thinking, Encourage teaching methods that foster active learning, collaboration, and self-reflection, Ensure schools have necessary resources, technology, and infrastructure to support metacognitive instruction, Establish a system to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of metacognitive skills integration in mathematics education. It will also benefit in the following ways: Metacognitive skills can enhance problem-solving abilities and mathematical understanding, Students will develop critical thinking skills, essential for real-world applications, Teachers will be equipped to adapt to changing educational landscape

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